

Basic concepts of the growth of motor development in gymnastics.

Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti Jismoniy Madaniyat kafedrası o'qituvchisi
(Asia International University)

E-mail: hikmatulloaefiyev@gmail.com

Annotation: Modern gymnastics extremely colorful. Great gymnastics from coordination complex, biological a lot power demanding system technical, physical, functional of athletes and psychological preparation level very high requirements puts Today's of the day high value gymnasts strength, strength, agility, flexibility and maximum durability like physical of adjectives incomparable step come out they are very busy, work ability developed to be a must Gymnastics multi-sport in types exercises perform on the way main objective obstacle gymnast body weight of boys and girls is considered One him from the place to another shift for strength to spend and certain powered mechanic the work needs to be done. In gymnastics of muscles absolute power not but relative power pointers they are important gymnast body per 1 kg of weight is determined. Exercises of complexity regularly grow up going because of modern sports gymnastics his own complicated coordination status did not lose without more and more more obvious expressed power services have being is going

Keyword: Motor development, Periods of motor development, Motor characteristics, General strength, Specific strength

Motor development

The development of the child's body is a complex continuous process with morphological, functional and biochemical changes, which has a clear sequence and cycle in different stages. In addition, the development of the child's body continues in stages; moreover, each subsequent age stage occurs during the final formation of the previous one. A child's development consists of two components: mental and physical development, which are closely related to each other; a delay in one of them can lead to a delay in the other. Plasticity is characteristic of the child's organism, thanks to which it acquires the ability to change under the influence of any conditions (external or internal) and to absorb the accumulated experience. Due to this unique feature, mental or physical functions can be compensated or restored when they are absent or underdeveloped

Emphasizing that it is time to acquire, balance and reduce motor skills of the body; In the same process, he explained the importance of growth, maturity, readiness and learning. Physical development of a person begins before birth and continues to grow in the subsequent period. Motor development occurs after physical development occurs. Previously formed as a reflex

Some of the movements continue throughout life as reflexes, while some become motor skills over time with proper use of the organs. At the core of motor development as an academic discipline is content related to views and principles related to growth, development, and motor movement.

At the end of general motor development, a person's progress in movement skills is determined. Parameters such as strength, speed, coordination, balance and agility can be improved with training programs designed to improve motor skills. Currently, the development of motor skills is given great importance and time. Although the development of movement skills depends entirely on the opportunity, motivation and training provided to the individual, it is fully accepted

that these skills do not develop by themselves.

Periods of motor development

Gallahue thought of "motor development" as a stage that begins in the womb and continues into later life, creating a four-stage model. Each period consists of different stages.

Periods of development

- Period of reflexive actions (0-1 years)
- The period of primitive movements (1-2 years old)
- Period of basic movements (2-7 years)
- Period of sports-related activities (7 years and older)

Period of reflexive actions (0-1 years)

Reflex actions occur during this period. It is observed in all fetuses and babies. Thanks to reflexes, the baby collects all the information about the environment and recognizes its body. Primitive reflexes that occur during reflexive movements (sucking, searching, grasping, plantar flexion, Babinski, etc.) provide more nutritional and protective functions, while reflexive movements associated with posture (stepping, crawling, pulling, parachute, support, etc.) is like a voluntary behavior and helps the body to stand upright.

The period of primitive movements (1-2 years old)

With the development of the central nervous system, control is primarily provided by the head and trunk, and secondly by the arms and legs. Primitive movements, known as the first step of voluntary movements, are observed at the age of 0-2 years. A child's ability to stand, crawl, and sit on its own shows the importance of maturity in its development. In addition to bone, muscle and nervous system development in the first two years of life, a child's movements result from the exercise opportunities that parents provide for their babies. Although primitive movements parallel maturation, they follow a predictable sequence in their emergence. Under normal conditions, this sequence does not change, but the appearance and speed of these movements may differ in each child. Genetic and environmental influences form the basis of these changes.

Period of basic movements (2-7 years)

This is a period of increased motor development that occurs during early childhood. Here the child reveals the ability to move his body; By using body parts and the coordination between them, they acquire different and complex skills. During the period of basic movements, the child develops the parameters of balance, locomotor and manipulative movements and learns to perform movements first one by one, and then simultaneously. The period of basic movements creates not only the basic characteristics of the movements, but also their individual styles and characteristics. Movement models are examined one by one and combinations of these movements are revealed and movements such as running, catching, throwing, kicking, jumping and rolling are combined. Movements form the basis of many sports networks. For example; Throwing something forward is a basic movement in sports like volleyball or tennis. The development of skills paves the way for sports activities.

Period of sports-related activities (7 years and older)

This stage is a continuation of the period of main actions. Actions in this part are goal-oriented. The skills acquired during the main activities can be combined with the rules and become joint activities. Explain with an example; Jumping and jumping skills learned during basic movements can be translated into a structured jump rope game that requires cooperation in this section.

The characteristics of the movement period associated with sports are;

- A high rate of growth is observed in achievement until adolescence.
- In order for the level of motor development to be perfect, it is important that basic movement skills are at their maximum.
- When starting to engage in sports activities aimed at ensuring the child's development, it is necessary to review the period of basic movements and work on mature movement skills.
- In order to acquire sports skills in the body, it is necessary to pay attention to the period of basic movements. During this time, skills should be consciously taught to the child.
- Coaches should prepare training programs based on the ability and development of athletes.
- Competitions can be organized for the motivation needed for athletes to master these skills very well and perform them perfectly.

Competitions are of great importance in the life of athletes. Success in competitions depends on experience.

Effects of gymnastics on motor characteristics

Nowadays, when technology is a complete part of life, children's mobility is limited to computer games, TV and phones.

Children's desire to be in constant motion, which is necessary for their physical, mental and emotional development, is consciously or unconsciously inhibited.

Children who play sports regularly develop personally and physically. Gymnastics plays an important role in the physical and motor development of children.

Regular participation in physical activity, gymnastics or training benefits body mass (body weight, fat-to-muscle ratio), bone mineralization and density, muscle development and strength, and cardiorespiratory system development. If gymnastics is done systematically, the body will remain physically healthy. This fitness improves endurance, muscle strength, flexibility, body composition and cardiovascular system. movements such as falling. equipment. All movements that make up gymnastics contribute to the child's cardio-respiratory system, muscle strength and endurance.

Various bridging exercises using different parts of the body, jumping exercises and stretching exercises to cool down the body at the end of the training will help improve the flexibility of the body.

In addition, regular participation in programmed training or physical activity ensures that athletes become healthy individuals. Being healthy is important in child development. This can be achieved almost with gymnastic exercises. As a result of research; The need for physical activity is understood and it has been shown that people who exercise in a programmed way have fewer health problems in later life.

Motor characteristics

Motor characteristics are strength, endurance, speed, flexibility and dexterity. The key to success in all sports is the specifics of the equipment required for the sport being used. Motor characteristics vary depending on the body's mobility and efficiency level. It is not acquired, it is innate and developed. The development of these characteristics occurs after a regular training program. It is determined by tests and strength checks that determine the level of development. The development of basic motor skills in all areas of sports is parallel to the training program that

we implement.

Strength- This is the ability to withstand resistance. It occurs as a result of the interaction of internal and external forces. Muscles, the strength of muscles and the contraction of these muscles create internal force, while the force between the surfaces of gravity and friction caused by the interaction of external factors creates external force. However, with a conscious reduction. nervous system, strength reaches the highest level that the athlete can achieve and exceeds his capabilities. It is expressed as weight lifting.

Strength in sports

General strength: This refers to the strength that considers the muscles as a whole and includes many muscles and muscle groups without specifying a specific branch. It includes training programs for developing the strength of all muscle groups of individuals who are new to the sport. If general strength, which is a prerequisite for specific strength, is not sufficiently developed to allow a person to perform effectively, it will adversely affect the athlete's development and performance.

Specific strength: This refers to the strength required by a particular sport and the sport. This ensures the development of strength for movements related to the main characteristics of the performed sport, not all muscle groups of the body. Training programs that include special strength begin with studies leading to the professionalization of sports and athletes at the end of the preparatory period.

During the last hundred years, sports gymnastics has achieved great success. If we compare the exercises performed by the champions of the first and last Olympic Games, the conclusion can be summed up in two words: miraculous progress! This development accelerated especially after the introduction of parolon mats, pits and simulators, as well as new methods, tools and technologies of teaching and training. In a relatively short historical period, the level of complexity of exercises, the quality of their performance, and training loads have increased on an amazing scale. Gymnastics technique has changed radically. In modern sports, a large number of colorful movements, which are different in terms of their structure, provided by different movements and different modes of activity, have been created. The same at the time of sports gymnastics The main criteria are sports as formed from the time starting from tradition the beam took This is the exercise their complexity composition and perform quality In gymnastics all in times gymnast what are doing and this how doing it evaluation object it happened. Sports gymnastics opponents with tool to the relationship did not enter without relatively unchanging in the circumstances executable coordination according to complex action and kin e matic of activities system stabilized sports to the group enters Other sports with in comparison , in gymnastics manager from actions consists of , n e gaki , many gymnastics in exercises competition to the rules according to hand and the legs right need to catch However this relatively simple manager x arakats space and in time mutually very sure coordinated to be , quite to himself situations own on time execution it is necessary Often this very complex , goals change quickly standing , time tight was in the circumstances done is increased . Same things perform space-time point of view in terms of and strength spending in terms of strictly measured actions using provided , others done increase for maximum strength impulse development is required , third character power requirements reasonable level to harmonize invitation is enough , the fourth for extraordinary agility , for while high level balance feeling necessary Of these bar a lot cases one exercise in itself embodied will be.

Used literature

1. Xayrullayevich, S. H. (2023). Use of Acrobatic Exercises and Their Terms In The Process of Teaching Gymnastics. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies* (2993-2599), 1 (9), 80–86.
2. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). SPORT GIMNASTIKASIDA HARAKATLAR KETMA-KELIGINING NAMOYON BO'LISHI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 478–491. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/tsru/article/view/3588>
3. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). АЭРОБНОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 449–456. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/tsru/article/view/3585>
4. Xayrullayevich, S. H. (2023). SPORTS ARE GYMNASTICS IN ACTION SERIES-BE THE MANIFESTATION OF COME. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1 (5), 465–477.
5. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). SPORTS ARE GYMNASTICS IN ACTION SERIES-BE THE MANIFESTATION OF COME. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 465–477. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/tsru/article/view/3587>
6. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2024). Gimnastikaning- ta'limni rivojlantiruvchi turlari. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(2), 77–83. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/tsru/article/view/4259>
7. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich. (2024). Gimnastika zallardagi talablar va jihozlar. "XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" Nomli Respublika Ilmiy-Amaliy Konferensiyasi, 2(1), 125–132. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/itftdm/article/view/3978>
8. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrulloevich. (2024). Gimnastikada himoya yordam berish va o'zini o'zi straxovka(himoya) qilish, jarohatlanishni oldini olish choralari sifatida. "XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" Nomli Respublika Ilmiy-Amaliy Konferensiyasi, 2(1), 116–124. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/itftdm/article/view/3977>
9. Sayfiyev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2024). Gimnastikaning sport turlari va sog'lomlashtiruvchi ahamiyati. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(1), 98–104. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/tsru/article/view/3824>
10. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). APPROACHES, BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS, PRINCIPLES AND METHODS OF WORK OF COACHES AND MANAGERS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 133–151. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-16>
11. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). GLOBALIZATION AND SPORTS INDUSTRY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 164–182. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-18>
12. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). SOCIAL SPORTS MARKETING. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-17>

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

13. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). RECOVERY STRATEGY IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 135–147. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-18>
14. Azamat Orunbayev, (2023) NONUSHTANING MASHQ BAJARISHGA TA'SIRI. *International journal of scientific researchers* 2(2), 3-6.
15. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). USING TECHNOLOGY IN A SPORTS ENVIRONMENT. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-07>
16. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). FITNES VA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA MURABBIYLIK YO'NALISHIGA KONTSEPTUAL YONDASHUV. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(8), 23–28. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/431>
17. Azamat Orunbayev. (2023). PANDEMIYA DAVRIDA MOBIL SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH VA FITNES DASTURLARI (PROGRAM). *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(7), 37–42. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/414>
18. Sayfiev Hikmatullo Xayrullayevich. (2023). Gimnastika zallarning talablari va sport zallar xususiyatlari. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 435–441. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/tsru/article/view/3580>
19. Sayfiyev, H. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL INSTRUCTIONS AND METHODS OF CONDUCTING EXERCISES IN A GYMNASTICS LESSON. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 255–259. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24329>
20. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2024). Gimnastika darsining maqsadlari, vositalari va uslubiy xususiyatlari. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(1), 90–97. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/tsru/article/view/3823>
21. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Jismoniy qobiliyatlarning rivojlanishi va jismoniy sifatlarning ko'chishi. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 379–393. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/tsru/article/view/3554>
22. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Physical education lessons in the process of unumpedagogik methods. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 345–354. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/tsru/article/view/3548>
23. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Physical downloads and the rest of fulfilling exercise mutual dependence. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 394–409. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/~niverta1/index.php/tsru/article/view/3556>
24. Ayubovna, S. M. (2023). Jismoniy qobiliyatlarning rivojlanishi va jismoniy sifatlarning ko'chishi. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1 (5), 379–393.
25. Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Gimnastika darsining maqsadlari, vositalari va uslubiy xususiyatlari. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2 (1), 90–97.
26. Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Gimnastika darsining maqsadlari, vositalari va uslubiy xususiyatlari. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2 (1), 90–97.
27. Ayubovna, S. M., & Xayrullayevich, S. H. (2023). YOSH BOLLALARDA SPORT SPORT.
28. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2024). Gimnastikaning- ta'limni rivojlantiruvchi turlari. *"XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM*

TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" Nomli Respublika Ilmiy-Amaliy
Konferensiyasi, 2(1), 100–107. Retrieved from
<https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/itftdm/article/view/3975>

29. Ayubovna, S. M. (2024). Gimnastika sport turining turlari va tasniflashi. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 2(1), 108-115.

30. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). Jismoniy tarbiyaning vositalariga va jismoniy mashqlar xarakteristikasi. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 370–378. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/tsru/article/view/3553>

31. Saidova Mahbuba Ayubovna. (2023). The pedagogical category of physical exercise. Spatial exercises. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 2(12), 509–518. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/rjtds/article/view/1774>

32. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). APPLICATIONS OF SPORT PSYCHOLOGY IN THE WORLD. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 107–120.

33. Sirojev, S. (2023). TEACHING ACTIVITIES AND PHILOSOPHY IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 235–243.

34. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF MUTUAL RESPECT AND KINDNESS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 215–225.

35. Sirojev, S. (2024). EFFECTS OF SOCIAL PHOBIA ON SPORTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 318–326.

36. Sirojev Shoxrux. (2023). STUDYING SPORTS PSYCHOLOGY. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 176–188.

37. Sirojev, S. (2024). EFFECTS OF WARM-UP AND STRETCHING EXERCISES ON PROPRIOCEPTION AND BALANCE. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2),

38. Yarasheva Dilnoza Ismail Qizi. (2023). TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL SKILLS IN SPORTS. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(10), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue10-16>

39. Yarashova, D. (2023). THE IMPACT OF PLAYING SPORTS IN EARLY CHILDHOOD ON SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 230–234. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24325>

40. Ярашева, Д. (2023, April). ФИТНЕС КАК ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies* (Vol. 2, No. 4, pp. 278-283).

41. Yarasheva, D. (2022). BOLALARDA MASHQ QILISHNING ANAMIYATI. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 19(1), 139-142.

42. Ярашева, Д. (2023). СТИЛИ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ НЕТРАДИЦИОННЫХ ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 19(5), 6-10.

43. Yarashova, D. (2023). STRENGTH TRAINING AND STRENGTH TRAINING IN CHILDREN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 211-215.

44. Dilnoza, Y. (2024). SOG'LOMLASHTIRUVCHI MASHG'ULOTLARNING TURLARI VA SAMARADORLIGI.

45. Dilnoza, Y. (2024). SOG'LOMLASHTIRUVCHI MASHG'ULOTLARNING TURLARI VA SAMARADORLIGI.
46. Akhrorjon Nuriddinov. (2023). PHYSICAL ACTIVITY, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(12), 189–200. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue12-25>
47. Akhrorjon Nuriddinov. (2023). MANAGING THE PROCESS OF TALENT DEVELOPMENT IN SPORTS ANATASIA. *American Journal Of Social Sciences And Humanity Research*, 3(11), 121–132. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajsshr/Volume03Issue11-15>
48. Nuriddinov, A. (2024). THE CONNECTION BETWEEN SPORT AND PHILOSOPHY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 308–317. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28042>
49. Bahodir o'g'li, N. A. (2023). YEVROPA MAMLAKATLARIDA YUQORI MALAKALI FUTBOLCHI VA MURABBIYLARNI TEXNIK TAKTIK HARAKATLARINI TADBIQ QILISH METODIKASI. *THEORY AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF RECENT RESEARCH*, 2(14), 187-189.
50. Bahodir o'g'li, N. A. (2023). JISMONIY TARBIYADA FAIR PLAYNING O'RNINI.
51. Nuriddinov, A. (2023). KARL MARX AND THE THOUGHTS OF CLASS THEORY ON SPORTS CULTURE. *MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH*, 2(12), 249–258. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10320828>
52. Nuriddinov, A. (2024). THE CONNECTION BETWEEN SPORT AND PHILOSOPHY. *MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH*, 3(1), 308–317. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10501012>
53. Bahodir o'g'li, N. A. (2023). NIMA UCHUN FUTBOL BUGUNGI KUNDA SPORT DEB ATALGANIDA BIRINCHI NAVBATDA AQLGA KELADI.
54. Dilnoza, Y. (2023). SUB'YEKTIV VA SPORT
55. Jalolov, T. (2023). UNDERSTANDING THE ROLE OF ATTENTION AND CONSCIOUSNESS IN COGNITIVE PSYCHOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(12), 839-843.
56. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). MATH MODULES IN C++ PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(12), 834-838.